

Scaling Long-Context LLMs via Unified KV Cache Optimization: A Comparative Study of Paged Attention and Quantization

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Abstract—The Key-Value (KV) cache is the dominant memory bottleneck in autoregressive large language model (LLM) inference, growing linearly with context length. This paper presents a systematic empirical study of three KV cache optimization strategies applied to Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 on a single NVIDIA A100 GPU: (1) a full-precision FP16 baseline using Hugging-Face Transformers, (2) custom INT8/INT4/INT3 quantization via a DynamicCache-compatible QuantizedKVCache class, and (3) vLLM’s PagedAttention. Across input lengths of 512–4096 tokens and output lengths of 32–128 tokens, we measure peak GPU memory, decode throughput (tokens/sec), time-to-first-token (TTFT), prefill latency, and total generation time. Our results show that naive KV quantization reduces memory by less than 2% while incurring 55–89% throughput degradation due to dequantization overhead on every attention step. In contrast, vLLM’s PagedAttention delivers a 2.0–2.5× throughput improvement over the FP16 baseline, at the cost of 2.2× higher peak memory reservation. These findings reveal a clear architectural hierarchy: memory-layout-based optimizations (PagedAttention) outperform tensor-compression-based approaches (quantization) under realistic single-batch inference conditions.

Index Terms—KV cache, large language models, PagedAttention, quantization, inference optimization, long-context, LLM serving

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

Large language models (LLMs) based on the transformer architecture have achieved remarkable performance across a wide range of natural language processing tasks. During autoregressive inference, a Key-Value (KV) cache stores intermediate attention states from previously processed tokens, enabling efficient token-by-token generation without recomputing attention over the entire context at each step. While this substantially reduces per-step compute, it introduces a critical memory bottleneck: KV cache memory grows linearly with sequence length. For a 7-billion-parameter model at FP16 precision with 32 attention layers, 32 key-value heads, and 128-dimensional heads, a single request with a 4096-token context requires approximately 1.6 GB of GPU memory just for the KV cache—on top of the ~14 GB required for model weights.

As LLM deployments scale to longer contexts (8k–32k tokens) and higher concurrency, this memory pressure causes out-of-memory (OOM) failures and severely limits throughput. Consequently, KV cache optimization has become one of the most active areas in LLM systems research.

B. Problem Statement

The core tension in KV cache optimization is between memory efficiency and computational overhead. Compression techniques such as quantization reduce the memory footprint of the cache but introduce dequantization cost at every attention step. Memory management techniques such as PagedAttention reduce fragmentation and improve allocation efficiency but require a separate inference engine. Understanding the practical trade-offs of these approaches under real workload conditions—varying context lengths, output lengths, and GPU constraints—is essential for guiding deployment decisions.

C. Objectives and Scope

This work addresses the following research questions:

- 1) How do KV cache quantization (INT8, INT4, INT3) and PagedAttention compare to the FP16 baseline in terms of throughput, latency, and memory consumption?
- 2) How does performance scale with input context length (512–4096 tokens)?
- 3) What are the practical trade-offs, and which technique is preferable under different conditions?

We scope our study to single-GPU, single-batch inference on a 7B-class instruction-tuned model (Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2) with input lengths ranging from 512 to 4096 tokens.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Review of Relevant Literature

PagedAttention (vLLM). Kwon et al. [1] introduced vLLM and PagedAttention, which manages the KV cache using a paging abstraction inspired by operating system virtual memory. Rather than pre-allocating a contiguous memory block per request, PagedAttention divides the KV cache into

fixed-size blocks allocated on demand. This eliminates memory fragmentation, enables memory sharing across requests, and dramatically improves GPU utilization under concurrent serving. The authors demonstrated up to $24\times$ higher serving throughput compared to HuggingFace Transformers.

KV Cache Quantization. KVQuant [2] introduced quantization techniques targeting the KV cache specifically, achieving sub-4-bit compression while maintaining model quality. Unlike weight quantization, KV quantization is applied dynamically at inference time and must account for the full distribution of key and value tensors across layers and positions. Our work implements a similar concept but exposes the dequantization overhead that arises in a non-kernel-fused Python-level implementation.

B. Gaps in Existing Research

Prior studies evaluate their techniques in isolation and often focus on throughput under high concurrency, without characterizing the latency trade-offs for single-batch inference. Our work fills this gap with a controlled benchmark that directly compares quantization and paging under identical hardware and model conditions.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

We generate synthetic prompts of controlled token lengths using a repetition-based prompt builder (`src/prompts.py`). A representative LLM-related paragraph is repeated and truncated to exactly reach the desired input token count (512, 1024, 2048, or 4096 tokens), as verified by the HuggingFace tokenizer. This ensures that input length is precisely controlled across all experimental conditions, isolating context-length effects from prompt-content effects. No external dataset is used for benchmarking; however, the prompt text reflects realistic natural-language token distributions relevant to LLM inference workloads.

B. Model Selection

All experiments use **Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2** [3], a 7.3-billion-parameter instruction-tuned model with grouped-query attention (GQA), sliding window attention (SWA), and a 32,768-token context window. The model is loaded in FP16 precision, occupying approximately 14.3 GB of GPU memory for weights. Mistral-7B was chosen because: (1) its size is representative of production-grade deployable models, (2) it supports the context lengths of interest, and (3) it fits in a single A100 80 GB GPU.

C. Optimization Procedures

We study three KV cache strategies, all targeting inference-time optimization only; no training modifications are made.

Baseline FP16. The standard HuggingFace `model.generate()` pipeline with `DynamicCache` (the default). A custom manual generation loop in `src/metrics.py` separates the prefill phase (full input

forward pass) from the decode phase (autoregressive token generation) for independent timing.

KV Cache Quantization. We implement a `QuantizedKVCache` class in `src/kv_quant.py` that extends `DynamicCache`. On each `update()` call, newly generated key and value tensors are quantized and stored as compressed chunks. On each attention retrieval, all stored chunks are dequantized, concatenated along the sequence dimension, and returned as full FP16 tensors. Three precisions are supported:

- **INT8:** Symmetric per-tensor quantization with scale = $\max(|x|)/127$. Memory: 1 byte/element ($2\times$ reduction vs FP16).
- **INT4:** Bit-packed symmetric quantization, packing two signed 4-bit values ($[-8, 7]$) per `uint8` byte via bit manipulation. Memory: 0.5 bytes/element ($4\times$ reduction vs FP16). Odd-length sequences are zero-padded.
- **INT3:** A 3-bit grid quantization using 8 levels $\{-4, -3, \dots, 3\}$, with scale = $\max(|x|)/3.0$. Values are stored in `int8` tensors (no true 3-bit packing), so memory footprint is equivalent to INT8.

PagedAttention (vLLM). The vLLM [1] inference engine is configured with `gpu_memory_utilization=0.9` on the same GPU. vLLM pre-allocates 90% of GPU VRAM for its KV block pool and manages allocation dynamically via a block manager. We use a single-request batch (`batch_size=1`) for a fair comparison with the other methods. The engine is initialized once and reused across all trials.

D. Profiling Tools and Methods

All timing is performed with CUDA-synchronized wall-clock measurements using Python’s `time.perf_counter()` bracketed with `torch.cuda.synchronize()` calls. GPU memory is tracked via `torch.cuda.max_memory_allocated()`, reset between trials using `torch.cuda.reset_peak_memory_stats()`. Model weight memory is measured once before the first forward pass and reported separately from peak memory (which includes KV cache and activations).

For vLLM, TTFT is extracted from request-level metrics (`metrics.time_to_first_token_ms`) when available, with a fallback to total generation time divided by output length. Results are logged incrementally to CSV files in `results2/raw/` using `src/logger.py`.

E. Evaluation Metrics

- **Total latency** (s): Wall-clock time from first input token to last generated token.
- **TTFT** (s): Time from request start to first generated token (prefill latency).
- **Prefill time** (s): Time for the initial full-sequence forward pass.
- **Decode throughput** (tokens/sec): Generated tokens divided by decode phase time.

- **Overall throughput** (tokens/sec): Total generated tokens divided by total time.
- **Peak GPU memory** (MB): Maximum `torch.cuda.max_memory_allocated()` during generation.
- **OOM flag**: Boolean indicating out-of-memory failure.

Each configuration is measured over 3 independent trials after 1 warmup trial.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

Hardware: NVIDIA A100 80 GB GPU on the NYU HPC cluster, single-node, single-GPU.

Software: PyTorch 2.x, HuggingFace Transformers 4.x, vLLM 0.4.x, Python 3.10, CUDA 12.x.

Model: mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2, FP16 precision.

Input lengths: 512, 1024, 2048, 4096 tokens.

Output lengths: 32, 64, 128 tokens.

Quantization bits: 8, 4, 3.

Trials: 3 per configuration (1 warmup discarded).

B. Performance Comparison

1) *Throughput vs. Input Length:* Table I summarizes decode throughput (tokens/sec) across methods and input lengths at a fixed output length of 128 tokens (3-trial medians).

TABLE I
DECODE THROUGHPUT (TOKENS/SEC) — OUTPUT: 128 TOKENS

Method	512	1024	2048	4096
Baseline FP16	27.60	27.20	27.20	27.92
Quant INT8	12.40	12.35	12.30	12.25
Quant INT3	12.48	12.40	12.35	12.30
Quant INT4	5.11	4.98	4.85	4.75
vLLM (Paged)	69.64	67.50	63.20	51.80

vLLM achieves 2.0–2.5× higher throughput than the FP16 baseline. INT8 and INT3 achieve only ~44% of baseline throughput. INT4 achieves only ~17% of baseline throughput.

2) *TTFT and Prefill Latency Scaling:* Table II shows how TTFT scales with input length at 128 output tokens. All methods exhibit linear TTFT growth, confirming that prefill complexity is $O(n^2)$ with sequence length.

TABLE II
TIME-TO-FIRST-TOKEN (TTFT, SECONDS)

Method	512	1024	2048	4096
Baseline FP16	0.048	0.087	0.167	0.337
Quant INT8/INT3	0.049	0.088	0.168	0.340
Quant INT4	0.052	0.093	0.180	0.361
vLLM (Paged)	0.047	0.085	0.162	0.320

TTFT grows approximately 7× from 512 to 4096 tokens (roughly 8× input growth), consistent with quadratic prefill attention. vLLM exhibits slightly lower TTFT due to fused CUDA kernels.

3) *Peak GPU Memory:* Table III shows peak GPU memory consumption including model weights and KV cache.

TABLE III
PEAK GPU MEMORY (MB) — OUTPUT: 128 TOKENS

Method	512	1024	2048	4096
Baseline FP16	14,553	14,731	15,127	15,921
Quant INT8	14,463	14,615	14,980	15,740
Quant INT3	14,463	14,615	14,980	15,740
Quant INT4	14,447	14,598	14,959	15,715
vLLM (Paged)	32,170	32,170	32,170	32,170

KV quantization achieves only 90–200 MB memory reduction compared to the baseline (0.6–1.4% savings), while vLLM pre-allocates 32.2 GB (2.2× the baseline peak) to provision its block pool.

4) *Total Latency at Fixed Output Length:* At 4096 input tokens and 128 output tokens, total generation times are:

- Baseline FP16: ~4.92 s (26.0 tokens/sec overall)
- Quant INT8: ~10.8 s (11.8 tokens/sec)
- Quant INT3: ~10.7 s (11.9 tokens/sec)
- Quant INT4: ~76.6 s (1.67 tokens/sec)
- vLLM: ~2.5 s (~51 tokens/sec)

INT4 is 15.6× slower than the FP16 baseline at the longest tested context. vLLM is 2.0× faster.

5) *Throughput vs. Output Length:* Fig. 1 illustrates how decode overhead grows with output length. FP16 decode throughput is stable (~28 tokens/sec) regardless of output length, while quantized methods show accumulating overhead: at 128 output tokens, INT4 decode throughput degrades to ~5 tokens/sec, indicating $O(L)$ dequantization cost per token where L is the accumulated KV sequence length.

Fig. 1. Decode throughput vs. output token count for each KV cache strategy (512-token input). Quantized methods degrade sharply as KV sequence grows (INT4: 5.1→1.7 tok/s); FP16 and vLLM remain stable.

C. Analysis of Results

Quantization dequantization bottleneck. The naive quantize-on-store / dequantize-on-retrieve approach implemented in `QuantizedKVCache` performs a full dequantization of all stored KV chunks for every attention computation

during decoding. At decode step t , the cache holds t chunks, so the dequantization cost grows as $O(t)$ per step, leading to $O(T^2)$ total decode overhead for T generated tokens. This explains why INT4 degrades catastrophically at longer outputs (~ 76 s for 128 tokens vs ~ 5 s for 32 tokens at 4096 input).

INT3 storage equivalence. The INT3 implementation stores quantized values in `int8` tensors without true 3-bit packing, making its memory footprint identical to INT8. The 3-bit quantization grid (8 levels) provides lower representational fidelity for the same storage cost.

vLLM memory trade-off. vLLM’s 32.2 GB pre-allocation reflects its policy of reserving 90% of GPU memory (0.9×80 GB ≈ 72 GB; minus model weights ≈ 14.3 GB, leaving ~ 57 GB for KV blocks). This large reservation enables high concurrency at scale but is wasteful for single-request workloads. Despite $2.2\times$ higher memory usage, vLLM delivers $2.0\text{--}2.5\times$ higher throughput via fused CUDA kernels and optimized memory access patterns.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Interpretation of Results

Our results reveal a fundamental distinction between two classes of KV optimization:

Tensor compression (quantization) reduces storage but adds compute overhead on every attention step. For the naive implementation studied here, the overhead completely dominates any memory bandwidth savings at the tested sequence lengths. This does not mean quantization is inherently ineffective—kernel-fused implementations such as those in KVQuant [2] can perform quantized matmuls directly without materializing FP16 tensors, avoiding this bottleneck.

Memory management (paging) does not reduce per-token KV memory but eliminates fragmentation, enables on-demand allocation, and unlocks batch-level optimizations (continuous batching, prefix sharing) that are inaccessible to HuggingFace Transformers. The throughput gain for a *single-batch* workload ($\sim 2\times$) is largely attributable to vLLM’s use of fused CUDA kernels and CUDA graph capture, not the paging mechanism itself.

B. Comparison with Previous Studies

Kwon et al. [1] reported up to $24\times$ throughput improvement over HuggingFace for multi-request workloads. Our single-request measurement ($2.0\text{--}2.5\times$) is lower because the primary benefit of PagedAttention—reduced memory fragmentation enabling larger effective batches—does not apply under `batch_size=1`. This is consistent with the original paper’s batched evaluation setup.

KVQuant [2] demonstrates that kernel-fused quantization can achieve near-lossless quality at sub-4-bit precision. Our results confirm the memory savings are achievable but expose the dequantization overhead that emerges in a non-fused Python-level implementation.

C. Challenges and Limitations

Single-batch evaluation. Our benchmarks use `batch_size=1`, which understates the benefits of PagedAttention (designed for high concurrency) and overstates the relative cost of quantization overhead (which scales better with larger KV budgets).

No kernel fusion. The `QuantizedKVCache` implementation dequantizes tensors in Python, introducing Python-level overhead. A CUDA-kernel-fused implementation would significantly reduce this cost.

INT3 storage. True 3-bit packing (e.g., via `uint8` arrays with bit manipulation across byte boundaries) is not implemented; the current INT3 uses INT8 storage, negating memory reduction.

No quality evaluation. We do not measure perplexity or task accuracy for quantized outputs. INT4 quantization may degrade generation quality, especially for precision-sensitive tasks.

Context length cap. Due to hardware constraints, experiments are limited to 4096-token inputs. Long-context behaviors (8k–32k) where quantization memory savings become more significant are not covered.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Summary of Findings

We benchmarked three KV cache optimization strategies—FP16 baseline, custom INT8/INT4/INT3 quantization, and vLLM PagedAttention—on Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 across 48 configurations (4 input lengths \times 3 output lengths \times 4 methods \times 3 trials). Key findings:

- 1) **KV quantization in a non-fused implementation is counter-productive.** INT8 and INT3 deliver only $\sim 44\%$ of baseline throughput with $<1.4\%$ memory savings. INT4 is $15.6\times$ slower than the baseline at 4096 tokens due to cumulative dequantization overhead.
- 2) **vLLM PagedAttention provides 2.0–2.5 \times throughput gain** over the FP16 baseline even for single-batch inference, at the cost of $2.2\times$ higher memory reservation.
- 3) **TTFT scales linearly with input length** (0.048 s at 512 tokens to 0.337 s at 4096 tokens) across all methods, reflecting quadratic prefill complexity.
- 4) **Peak GPU memory grows at ~ 370 MB per doubling of input length** for the FP16 baseline, consistent with theoretical KV cache size predictions.

B. Contributions

- A reproducible, configuration-driven benchmarking harness for KV cache optimization, open-sourced with YAML-driven sweeps, CSV logging, and a Streamlit visualization dashboard.
- An implementation of `QuantizedKVCache` (INT8/INT4/INT3) compatible with HuggingFace’s `DynamicCache` interface, exposing the dequantization bottleneck in Python-level implementations.

- A direct, fair comparison of quantization and paging under identical hardware and model conditions, producing practical guidance for practitioners.

C. Recommendations for Future Work

- 1) **Kernel-fused quantized attention:** Implement INT4/INT8 quantized KV attention directly in CUDA (or via Triton) to eliminate Python-level dequantization overhead and realize the theoretical memory-bandwidth savings.
- 2) **True 3-bit packing:** Implement bit-manipulation-based packing of 3-bit values to achieve the $5.3\times$ theoretical memory reduction over FP16.
- 3) **High-concurrency evaluation:** Benchmark PagedAttention at batch sizes of 4, 8, 16 requests to capture its primary advantage over single-request baselines.
- 4) **Combined optimization:** Evaluate quantized KV caches within vLLM’s block manager (quantized paging) for potential multiplicative benefits.
- 5) **Extended context lengths:** Push benchmarks to 8k–32k tokens where KV cache growth is the dominant memory consumer and quantization memory savings become substantial.
- 6) **Quality-accuracy trade-offs:** Add perplexity and downstream task accuracy evaluation for quantized outputs to characterize the fidelity-efficiency frontier.

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